

Distribution of Electrolytes Across a Semipermeable Membrane in presence of Negatively Charged Colloidal Iron Oxide

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Hydration value in the case of negatively charged iron oxide sol has been determined by studying the distribution of chloride as a reference substance across a semipermeable membrane. Neglecting the membrane equilibrium effect, the value of hydration is 36 mM of water per g. of iron oxide.

The properties of colloidal sols are governed by the charge as well as the hydration of the micelles. The latter was determined previously in the case of iron oxide sol¹, aluminium oxide sol², and zirconium oxide sol³. It would be interesting to ascertain the possibility of preparing negatively charged sols of the above oxides and to study their properties. In the present investigation, negatively charged iron oxide sol has been prepared and the hydration of the micelles has been determined by studying the distribution of a reference substance across a semipermeable membrane.

EXPERIMENTAL

Negatively charged ferric oxide sol was prepared by peptising freshly precipitated ferric hydroxide by minimum quantity of NH_4OH in presence of considerable quantity of sucrose⁴⁻⁵. It is advisable to add sucrose to ferric chloride solution in the initial stage of preparation of the sol. The freshly precipitated coagulum was freed of other impurities by repeated washing or centrifuging of the coagulum. The excess of ammonia was removed by heating the sol on a water bath at 60°. The sol, thus prepared, is fairly stable if preserved in dark. The sol could not be further purified by dialysis as removal of sucrose rendered it unstable. The presence of sucrose in considerable quantity is essential for the stability of the sol. Chloride was estimated as silver chloride. An aliquot portion of the sol was coagulated by magnesium sulphate. The filtrate with its washings was employed for the determination of the chloride content.

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1. Trivedi and Divatia, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1953, **37A**, 33.
2. Trivedi *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1957, **34**, 683.
3. Trivedi *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1961, **38**, 291.
4. Mehrotra and Sen, *ibid.*, 1927, **4**, 117.
5. Sen and Dhar, *Kolloid Z.*, 1923, **33**, 193, 202.

Membrane Equilibrium Experiments

The sols, prepared as above, were kept in collodion bags, suspended in water for three weeks at the room temperature, until equilibrium was established, care being taken to avoid evaporation and to protect the sol from light. The collodion bags were prepared as before⁶. After attainment of equilibrium, the sol inside (I) and much weaker sol outside (E) were analysed for different constituents. Results of the membrane equilibrium experiments are recorded below.

TABLE I

Expt. No.	Conc. of iron oxide (g./litre).		Conc. of chloride (m.e./litre).		D.	S.H.V.
	(I).	(E).	(I).	(E).		
1	36.10	2.800	108.6	109.7	1.179	3.3
2	38.00	1.100	110.5	113.7	1.311	3.7
3	31.12	0.845	111.4	114.1	1.279	3.8
4	34.63	3.535	112.7	116.1	1.062	4.6
5	31.12	4.115	108.6	112.9	0.952	5.1
6	35.25	1.250	110.5	113.3	1.345	3.6
7	36.98	1.400	107.2	110.6	1.157	4.2
8	41.50	2.540	110.3	115.8	0.961	5.1
9	31.57	0.425	85.7	88.3	1.058	4.6
10	33.50	0.880	88.8	91.3	1.191	4.1
						Mean 4.2

DISCUSSION

When iron oxide sol, containing ammonium chloride as a reference substance, is kept in a collodion bag and allowed to equilibrate with a diffusate outside the bag, there is an unequal distribution of chloride across a semipermeable membrane. This may be attributed to the following factors. The amount of chloride per unit volume is less within the bag than that outside the bag due to (a) establishment of the Donnan membrane equilibrium effect and (b) the volume occupied by the colloidal micelles, *i.e.* the volume of colloidal iron oxide including water attached to it (which does not function as a solvent for chloride). On the other hand, the adsorption of chloride ion, if any, by the micelles will lead to the increase of chloride ion, as compared to that outside the bag. The chloride ions are not, however, likely to be adsorbed by the negatively charged iron oxide micelles⁷.

Table I shows that the concentration of chloride outside the bag (E) is greater than that inside (I). Unequal distribution of chloride across a semipermeable membrane may allow us to calculate either (a) the hydration or (b) the membrane equilibrium effect provided that the other is known. Thus hydration of micelles may be calculated if membrane-equilibrium effect is allowed for. A suitable method to estimate the membrane-equilibrium effect could not be devised. If the concentration of the diffusible ions is much greater than that of the non-diffusible ions, the membrane-equilibrium effect will, however, be of

6. Hatschek, "Laboratory Manual of Elementary Colloid Chemistry", 1920, p. 22.

7. Bolam and Trivedi, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1942, **38**, 140; cf. Ref. No. 1.

8. McBain, "Colloid Science", 1950, p. 214.

lesser importance as compared to the hydration effect⁹. In the present case, the concentration of diffusible ion is several times more than that of the non-diffusible ions. Besides, only a fraction of the latter may contribute to the membrane-equilibrium effect⁹; if it is neglected, the difference in chloride concentration outside (E) and inside (I) the membrane may be attributed to the hydration of micelles. From the data, the apparent density (D) and the specific hydrodynamic volume (S.H.V.) can be calculated¹⁰. Taking the average value of S.H.V. as 4.2 and density of Fe_2O_3 as 4.913¹¹, there will be 36 mM of non-solvent water to 1 g. of iron oxide, *i. e.* about 6 moles = $\left(\frac{36 \times 160}{1000} = 6\right)$ of water per mole of iron oxide.

This may be compared to hydration of the micelles in the case of positively charged iron oxide sols (441mM of water per g. of ferric oxide¹). The micelles in the case of positively charged sols are much more hydrophillic and more stable than those in the case of negatively charged iron oxide sols. Again, the stability of negatively charged sol is due to presence of sucrose in the system. It will be interesting to investigate the mechanism of stabilisation of the sol by sucrose molecules.

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9. Bjerrum, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1924, **110**, 658.
10. Trivedi and Patani, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1954, **40A**, 119.
11. Mellor, "A Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", 1947, Vol. **13**, p. 789, Longmans, U.K.